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Appraisal of Thuggery, Violence and Socio-political Conflict in Lagos State during 2023 Nigerian General Elections

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Abstract

Sociopolitical conflict, thuggery and electoral violence are great challenges of many democratic societies, especially in developing countries. In Nigeria particularly, these societal anomalies keep devastating most major elections in the country. The foundation of electoral violence in Nigeria has often been attributed to social and political marginalization, poverty, unemployment and under-employment and other excruciating human conditions. This paper attempts to examine socio-political violence and determine the causes and effects of violent thuggery on Lagos state during 2023 Nigerian general elections. The research adopts World Systems Theory and Social Conflict Theory particularly to elucidate the discourse. For the purpose of this study a minimum percentage of 0.0035 of the total registered voters in Lagos state (7,060,195) were sampled randomly by means of online form, amounting to approximately two hundred and forty-eight (248) items of a questionnaire. Corruption, unemployment, inadequate security and lack of integrity from the electoral umpire (Independent National Electoral Commission) ranked highest as the major causes of thuggery and electoral violence in the country. Effects

found include civil unrest, population displacement, disability, loss of property, and death. The study recommends decentralisation of Nigerian security system to promote prompt and effective containment of violence associated with general elections. It prescribes further mitigation of political exclusion economic deprivation, equitable resource distribution, and also embarking on implementation of poverty reduction policies.

Keywords: Socio-political, Conflict, Thuggery, Violence, 2023 Nigerian General Elections

Introduction

Elections are very important pillars of what democracy stands for and have become the commonly accepted means of legitimating government. Once any part of the processes of an election is flawed, it becomes an invitation to anarchy and violence in the state. This may snowball into political instability (Taylor., Pevehouse, & Straus, 2017). Elections are held in nearly all countries in the contemporary world with the exception of a handful of states including Brunei, China, Eritrea, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and South Sudan, that are not practising the typical Western democracy. The employment of elections to select leaders ought to provide a nonviolent alternative to the use of force, and it ought to be a mechanism that allows citizens greater say over how they are governed. Yet in practice, these expectations often fail to conform to reality.

Many elections, especially those in democracies that are not yet fully consolidated are fraught with significant levels of violence during the campaign period, on polling day or in the aftermath of voting. Electoral violence can result in casualty tolls that meet the threshold of civil war within days or weeks. When this occurs, it can undo years of peace building and development work, it can undermine democratic institutions, and it can even trigger civil war. For instance, post-election violence after the 2010 polls in Ivory Coast led to more than 1,000 civilian deaths, one million internally displaced persons and 100,000 refugees in neighbouring countries (Colombo, D'Aoust, & Sterck, 2019). Recent elections in Afghanistan, Bangladesh, India, Iraq, Kenya, Nigeria, Pakistan, and Zimbabwe were similarly accompanied by high levels of conflict. Violence, even at levels below that witnessed in the most egregious cases, undermines the democratic character of elections by substituting free choice with coercion and by deterring participation. Education being the pillar of all developmental strides of any country is a process whereby all citizens of the state acquire skills, knowledge and attitudes to enable them become functional members of the society. Education is seen as a key for transformation of individual and national development (Adogbeji and Oyovwe-Tinuoye, 2018). To support this assertion, Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) in her National Policy on Education states that, education in Nigeria is an instrument "par excellence" for national development. Education is designed purposely to assist individuals to develop their skills and abilities and fulfil their potential to live

meaningful lives. Civic education is the near concept of education that has direct bearing with education of citizenry to become good players and law abiding in the political arena that is rounded up with conducting elections.

Elections have been held in Nigeria for over sixty years, although severally punctuated by military coups. Yet, despite its aim of allowing for peaceful transfer of power, elections held in Nigeria are known for substantial violence from the outset. When force intrudes into electoral processes, something is seriously amiss with democratic institutions and must be seriously looked into to avert problems that may arise as a consequence of the tampered electoral process.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to critically examine the nature of the 2023 Nigerian general elections in Lagos, Nigeria. In order to achieve this, a number of objectives are set for the study, which are to:

- 1) identify the causes of thuggery and violence recorded during 2023 general elections in Lagos State.
- 2) determine the effects of thuggery and violence on elections in Lagos State.
- 3) determine the ways in which electoral violence can be mitigated in such a place and time.

Research Questions

This research is guided by the following questions:

- 1) What causative factors could be adduced to electoral violence in Lagos state in 2023 general elections in Lagos State?
- 2) What outcomes emanated from socio-political violence in the course of 2023 general elections in Lagos State?
- 3) How can electoral violence be mitigated?

Conceptual Review

Conceptualization of Electoral Violence

Electoral-related violence comprises threats of coercion, physical or bodily harm and acts of intimidation perpetrated to affect or hinder an electoral process in an electoral context. When these acts are carried out, they affect the electoral process, thus may directly or indirectly influence the election process in a manner such as disruption voting pattern, and delay or derail of the outcome of the elections. Electoral violence is a form of political violence exhibited before, during and after election which often take the nature of political motivated kidnapping, killing, ballot box snatching, armed attacks on perceived opponent and the officers of electoral umpire as well as electoral stakeholders, burning of collation centres and offices for the purpose of gaining political

advantage. Pre-election violence is often more destructive in Africa, while violence on the day of election always come in form of attacks on electoral officers, ballot snatching, voter intimidation, manipulation of electoral outcome, while violence after the election comes in form of protest, burning of facilitates and electoral materials (Straus and Taylor, 2009). Electoral violence happens in form of arson, assassination, looting, and attacks on those involved in the electoral process such the media, voters, a candidate standing for an election, destroying electoral materials and campaign rallies (Onapajo, 2014).

Electoral violence is a deliberate strategy to effective pool away from the opponents from voting thus keep the other political party an advantage (Collier and Vicente, 2008). Similarly electoral violence as mental, physical structural acts targeted at blackmailing political opponent during the electoral process with the motive of shaping the electoral outcome towards a certain direction (Albert, 2007).

The Distinctiveness and Overview of Electoral Violence

The history of elections in Nigeria dates back to 1922 with the introduction of Clifford Constitution (Tamuno, 1966). The first recorded electoral violence in post-colonial Nigeria occurred in 1964 (Adesote & Abimbola, 2014). There were also violent conflicts in parts of Northern Region especially between supporters of the Northern People's Congress (NPC) and supporters of other parties, mainly the Northern Elements Progressive Union (NEPU) and Action Group (AG). The United Progressive Grand Alliance (UPGA) resolved to boycott the elections (Adesote & Abimbola, 2014). The Western Region became the battle ground amongst the NNDP, NPC and AG-UPGA. The upheavals led to the first military coup on January 15, 1966. This coup marked the end of the First Republic (Oluwabiyi & Duruji, 2021).

Subsequent elections that followed were the 1979 and 1983 which ushered in Alhaji Shehu Shagari as the President in 1979 and 1983, and the legislators of the Second Republic. Again, the elections were marred by irregularities and corruption, these sparked up huge magnitude of post-election violence. With Babangida's transition programme on course, a general election was organised in 1993. The 1993 elections were believed to be the freest and fairest ever conducted in Nigeria. (Emelifeonwu, 1999) Chief M.K.O. Abiola of the Social Democratic Party was assumed to have won the election. The annulment of the election by the military junta was greeted with stiff opposition and thus, led to certain political unrest. Chief Abiola declared himself President, which further exacerbated the tension and increased instability in Nigeria till the demise of Chief M.K.O Abiola (Tiamiyu, 2020). Following General Sani Abacha sacking the Interim Government headed by Chief Shonekan, General Abdulsalami Abubakar took over the saddle and returned the Nigeria to the 4th Republic on 29th May, 1999 with Chief Olusegun Obasanjo as the President of the Federal Republic and

Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of Nigeria. His government organised the 2003 election, which was marred by irregularities and conflict in almost every state of the federation. He handed over to President Umaru Ya'Adua who openly condemned the election that brought him into power, describing it as a flaw in 2007. President Jonathan organised the 2015 general election, which also, like the previous election was violence-ridden (Adesote & Abimbola, 2014).

Good governance in Nigeria and its ability to maintain sustainability is prevented by mainly electoral violence, which takes place during most, if not all the elections. In 2007, several electoral violence incidences took place. Approaching the 2007 elections, there were a lot of murder cases which took place. The 2011 general elections were better handled than the general elections that took place in 2003 and 2007, which happened under the fourth republic. However, in the 2011 elections, violence still occurred before, during and after the elections. The former President Olusegun Obasanjo did say that the elections during that period were a “do or die” situation. In other words, this motivated the voters who were on his side and the other people of Nigeria to engage in violence of which they did partake in (Bekoe 2017).

Thuggery and electoral violence are inflicted by political actors and/or their cronies to purposefully influence the process and outcome of elections, and it involves coercive acts against humans, property, and infrastructure (Harish and Toha, 2019). It can happen in all parts of the electoral cycle, including at the announcement of elections, party primaries, and voter registration, and it can be promoted by both state and non-state actors (Pevhouse and Straus, 2017). However, violence associated with elections can generate significant casualties and form part of an escalator process toward civil crisis. Operationally, election violence can be defined as any act of violent behaviour carried out in the way of supporting activities including pre, during and post-election periods such as use of force to disrupt political meetings and voting at polling stations, or the use of hazardous arms to threaten voters and other electoral actors, or to cause bodily damage or hurt to any human being connected with the electoral procedure.

A survey of relevant data-sets indicates that, a substantial proportion of elections across the globe witness at least some violence (Birch, Ursula and Höglund, 2020). The Countries at Risk of Election Violence (CREV) as the data estimated are over three quarters (78%) of elections in the countries deemed to be in risk of violence experience at ten violent events, that is while the Electoral Contention and Violence (ECAV) data report that more than three violent events in over 50% of elections had deadly violence event which is approximately 30% of elections (Daxecker, Amicarelli and Jung, 2019).

Structural Violence

Structural violence is a permanent state of violence, which is embedded in the social, political and economic structures that make up a society. Outing to the absence of

concrete person and its camouflaged nature, it is also known as indirect violence. The structural violence is often accepted as norms in the society. Primarily, structural violence is the result of hierarchical relations within and between societies that privilege those who are on top and oppress, exploit and dominate those who are at the bottom. Johan Galtung describes the mechanisms, and the forms of structural violence, which are: exploitation, penetration, segmentation, marginalisation, and fragmentation. These concepts are presented as argued by Galtung. Exploitation is based on unjust economic and social relations. It means nothing more than just a situation of ‘unequal exchange’ in which the ‘top dogs’ or the elite, draw substantially more profit from the interaction taking place within this structure than the ‘underdogs’ or the people excluded from development. A structure of violence not only leaves its marks on the human body, but also affects the mind and the soul.

Penetration involves the implantation of agents of the powerful within the collective ‘underdogs’. In a nutshell, with the help of penetration, elements of the ‘top dog’ or elite ideology reach the consciousness of the underdog or exploited sections of society. The penetration of the ideology is linked to segmentation.

Segmentation allows the underdog only a limited view of reality. It acts to obscure the true nature of the relationship between strong and weak. The segmentation is the result of two processes, marginalisation and fragmentation.

Marginalisation and Fragmentation exclude the peripheral agents from the centre and from each other, creating greater disharmony within the periphery than within the centre, while simultaneously preventing the interests of the exploited within the periphery from coinciding with the exploited within the centre.

In the similar vein, Dr. Martin Luther King Jr. speaks about the Giant Triplets i.e. racism, materialism and militarism as structural forces that propagate violence or the causes of all violence. Since indirect violence is deeply rooted in pervasive societal forces, its effects are as diverse as racism, poverty, hunger, sexism, violation of human rights and militarism.

Structural violence is latent as well as manifest. Moreover, it increases the latent potential for violence, such as highly tense situations which reduce individual’s capacity to pursue their objectives.

Theoretical Review

This article adopts two theories namely Social Conflict Theory and World Systems Theory explained concisely as follows.

Social Conflict Theory

Social conflict theory is a Marxist-based social theory which states that social systems reflect the vested interests of those who own and control resources. The people in power

use the political and economic institutions to exploit groups with less power. This causes the rest of society to become alienated or psychologically separated from the people in power. Revolutions occur to break down the social and economic separation between the people in power and the exploited people "to achieve equity and social unity".

Conflict theorists view conflicts as an engine of change, since conflict produces contradictions which are sometimes resolved, creating new conflicts and contradictions in an ongoing dialectic. In the classic example of historical materialism, Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels argue that all of human history is the result of conflict between classes, which evolved over time in accordance with changes in society's means of meeting its material needs.

World Systems Theory

World Systems Theory is a macro-sociological perspective that seeks to explain that wealthy countries benefit from other countries and exploit those countries' citizens. In contrast to dependency theory, however, this model recognizes the minimal benefits that are enjoyed by low status countries in the world system. The theory originated with sociologist Immanuel Wallerstein, who suggests that the way a country is integrated into the capitalist world system determines how economic development takes place in that country.

In Wallerstein's views, the world economic system is divided into a hierarchy of three types of countries: core, semi-periphery, and periphery. Core countries (e.g., U.S., Japan, Germany) are dominant, capitalist countries characterized by high levels of industrialization and urbanization. Core countries are capital intensive, have high wages and high technology production patterns and lower amounts of labour exploitation and coercion. Peripheral countries (e.g., most African countries and low-income countries in South America) are dependent on core countries for capital and are less industrialized and urbanized. Peripheral countries are usually agrarian, have low literacy rates and lack consistent Internet access. Semi-peripheral countries (e.g., South Korea, Taiwan, Mexico, Brazil, India, Nigeria, South Africa) are less developed than core nations but more developed than peripheral nations. They are the buffer between core and peripheral countries.

Core countries own most of the world's capital and technology and have great control over world trade and economic agreements. They are also the cultural centres which attract artists and intellectuals. Peripheral countries generally provide labour and materials to core countries. Semi-peripheral countries exploit peripheral countries, just as core countries exploit both semi-periphery and periphery. Core countries extract raw materials with little cost. They can also set the prices for the agricultural products that peripheral countries export regardless of market prices, forcing small farmers to abandon their fields because they can't afford to pay for labour and fertilizer. The

wealthy in peripheral countries benefit from the labour of poor workers and from their own economic relations with core country capitalists.

Review of Empirical Studies

Muhammad Aminu Kwasau (2022) came up with some findings namely, that thuggery has a serious negative impact on the political development of Zaria Local Government Area of Kaduna state; that the emergence of thuggery in the study area has undermined the legitimacy of the elected candidates and threatened democratic stability in Zaria Local Government Area of Kaduna state; and a lot of effort has been put in place by government through programmes and law enforcement agencies towards the control and prevention of possible future re-emergence in the study area.

In another piece on *Appraisal of the 2019 Post-Electoral Violence in Nigeria*, Timothy & Omolegbe (2019) opined that the 2019 general election in Nigeria witnessed one most violence post-electoral outcome ever witness in the history of the democratic dispersion in the country. He identified leading causes of this violence as ethnicity and sectional in politics, in-depth ignorance, political impunity, lack of internal democracy, negative perception inflammatory campaign. Article urgent need for amendment of the electoral act thereby making provision for electronic voting system and straightening provision and enforcement of the electoral offenses section as well as re-strategised the security architecture for elections in the country.

Further, Nlemchukwu & Chioma (2019) recommended after their findings that Government agencies such as the National Orientation Agency (NOA) should be made to be functional in carrying out their responsibilities. Government can partner with the civil society in enlightening the citizenry on the need for violent free elections. The provisions of employment opportunities are highly recommended. Most people who are usually involved in electoral violence of all nature are unemployed/underemployed youths who the corrupt politicians see as the best for their bid. Unemployment renders a person hopeless and makes him a veritable and available tool for political machinations. The bill for the establishment of Electoral Offences Commission should be passed without delay. This will help in the speedy trial of electoral offenders to serve as deterrent to future violent actors.

Statement of the Problem

No doubt, scholarship on elections in Nigeria is extensive. However, there is still gap in knowledge about causes and effects of the last conducted Nigerian general election in Lagos state, and how manifestation of violence-stained sanctity of the political action, as well as possibly tilted the election in certain ways. This is clearly and concisely the gap this paper intends to fill.

Methodology

The research is conducted largely relying on administration of a questionnaire, as well as secondary sources. For the purpose of this study a minimum percentage of 0.0003 of the total registered voters in Lagos state (7,060,195) were sampled randomly, amounting to approximately a minimum of 212 (Two hundred and twelve) items of a questionnaire administered either online (by means of Google forms) or physically on registered voters in the state.

Data Collection and Analysis

The major types of data used for the study is primary data which gathered using a structured questionnaire were analysed quantitatively and qualitatively. The other data type used which is secondary is on population and number of registered voters that were collected from the database of the National Census Board and the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC).

The data collected for this study with the use of the aforementioned instrument were distilled using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software for the processing of data, in which the data were coded into the computer. On the other hand, descriptive and inferential analyses were used for data analysis. Descriptive analysis to be adopted included the use of frequency and percentage tables, pictures, cross tabulations among others. All this was used to analyse the socioeconomic characteristics of respondents such as sex, age, marital status, educational status, occupation and monthly income distribution.

Likert scale was also used to ascertain the level of agreement to perceived causes and effects of thuggery and violence on general elections in Nigeria using Lagos as a case study. To calculate the agreement, respondents were subjected to rate level of agreement using strongly agree, agreed, not sure, disagree and strongly disagree.

Strongly agree takes 5, agree takes 4, not sure takes 3, disagreed is 2 and strongly disagree is 1. Each of the frequency for each satisfaction level will be used to multiply the listed number rate aforementioned.

The following are the terms that will be used during the course of calculation of the satisfaction levels: CWV= Cumulative weight value; NR = Number of respondents; RSI = Resident Satisfaction Index; \bar{X} = Mean value; D = Deviation; SD = Standard deviation

Table 1: Description of Research Instrument(s)

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Types of Data</i>	<i>Instrument of data collection</i>	<i>Method of Data Analysis</i>	<i>Sources of Data</i>
1	Examine the socio-economic characteristics of electoral participants.	LGA age, gender, ethnicity, marital status, level education, occupation, income.	Questionnaire	Descriptive statistics; Frequency count and percentage, cross tabulation	Primary
2	Determine the causes of thuggery and violence on elections	Activities that attract electoral thuggery violence.	Questionnaire	Descriptive statistics; Frequency count and percentage, cross tabulation and likert scaling.	Primary
3	Identify effects of thuggery and violence on elections.	List of common effects of violence on elections and level of occurrence.	Questionnaire	Frequency count and percentage and Likert scaling.	Primary
4	Suggestions to reduce electoral thuggery and violence.		Questionnaire	Descriptive statistics; Frequency count and percentage, cross tabulation, and likert scaling	Primary

Source: Authors' Work, 2023

Results and Discussion of Findings

This segment presents the result of study summarized in tabular forms and charts for easy references and analysis. It also shows answers to research questions for this research.

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondent

The table 2 presents the socio-economic characteristics.

Table 2: Socio-economic Characteristics of Respondents

Age	Below 18years	18-30 years	31-40 years	41-60 years	Above 60		
	12 (4.8%)	196 (79%)	26 (10.5%)	8(3.2%)	6 (2.4%)		
Gender	Male	Female					
	142 (57.3%)	106 (42.7%)					
Ethnicity	Yoruba	Igbo	Hausa	Others			
	176 (71%)	28 (11.3%)	18 (7.3%)	26 (10.5%)			
Marital status	Single	Married	Divorced	Widowed			
	206 (83.1%)	26 (10.5%)	10 (4%)	6 (2.4%)			
Level of Education	No Formal Education	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary			
	10 (5.4%)	4 (1.6%)	18 (7.3%)	216 (87.1%)			
Occupation	Trading	Civil servant	Professional	Artisan	Student	Others	
	20 (8.1%)	6 (2.4%)	32 (12.9%)	6 (2.4%)	148 (59.7%)	36(14.4%)	
Average Monthly Income	Below 20,000	20,000-30,000	30,000-40,000	40,000-50,000	50,000-90,000	Above 100,000	No Response
	44(18.2%)	36(14.9%)	18(7.4%)	22(9.1%)	28(11.6%)	40 (16.5%)	54 (22.3%)

Source: Authors' Field Work, 2023

Research Question One: What causative factors could be adduced to electoral violence in Lagos state in 2023 general elections?

The table below presents the Likert scaling results when respondents were asked to rank the major causes of electoral violence and thuggery. This factor ranges from poverty, unemployment, corruption, peer influence, cultism, inadequate voter education, inadequate security, tribalism/ethnicity, misinterpretation of politics, natural lack of democratic culture in Nigerians and lack of integrity from the electoral umpire (INEC).

As indicated in the table corruption, unemployment, inadequate security and lack of integrity from the electoral umpire (INEC) ranked highest with 0.304252, 0.271994, 0.094575 and 0.01393 respectively. Meaning respondents agreed more that these factors are the main causes of electoral violence and thuggery (significant causes of violence and thuggery on Nigerian general elections) meanwhile respondents rated Misinterpretation of politics, Cultism, Tribalism/ Ethnicity, Lack of democratic culture and Inadequate voters education do not really influence tourism (not significant) with -0.01026, -0.026393, -0.05865, -0.05865 and -0.08284 ratings respectively.

It can also be deduced from the table that the factors with the highest negative index are poverty and peer influence with the values -0.15543 and -0.292522, this implies that respondents believe that these factors have the least significant influence on violence and thuggery on Nigerian general elections.

Table 3: What are the causes of socio-political violence in the course of 2023 general elections?

SN		RATING					NR	CWV	RSI	X̄
		SA	A	NS	D	SD				
1.	Poverty	780	152	90	12	0	248	1034	4.169355	-0.15543
2.	Unemployment	880	184	72	4	0		1140	4.596774	0.271994
3.	Corruption	910	168	66	4	0		1148	4.629032	0.304252
4.	Peer influence									
		390	432	162	16	0		1000	4.032258	0.292522
5.	Cultism	620	328	102	16	0		1066		
									4.298387	0.026393
6.	Inadequate voter education	620	288	120	20	4		1052	4.241935	-0.08284
7.	Inadequate Security	730	272	84	8	2		1096	4.419355	0.094575
8.	Tribalism/ Ethnicity	630	296	120	8	4		1058	4.266129	-0.05865
9.	Misinterpretation of politics	610	336	120	4	0		1070	4.314516	-0.01026
10.	Lack of democratic culture	570	360	120	8	0	1058	4.266129	-0.05865	
11.	Lack of integrity from electoral umpire (INEC)	700	256	102	16	2	1076	4.33871	0.01393	
	TOTAL							47.57258	Mean=	4.32478

Source: Authors' Field Work, 2023

Research Question Two: What outcomes emanated from socio-political violence in the course of 2023 general elections in Lagos State?

The fact that injuries and violence go hand-in-hand is further buttressed in the Likert scale in Table 4. As clearly shown in the table respondents rated injuries to have the highest index of 0.166331 followed closely by death (0.16633) and loss of properties (0.126008). All other listed effect such as Displacement of people, Psychological stress, Disability, Civil Unrest had negative index values of -0.02722, -0.05948, -0.09173 and -0.11996 meaning respondents believe it be the least significant effect.

Table 4: Effects of Electoral Thuggery and Violence

SN		RATING					NR	CWV	RSI	X-X
		SA	A	NS	D	SD				
		5	4	3	2	1				
a	Civil Unrest	540	360	123	4	0	248	1027	4.141129	-0.11996
b	Death	730	272	84	12	0		1098	4.427419	0.16633
c	Destruction of health services	510	368	123	16	0		1017	4.100806	-0.16028
d	Disability	470	440	114	8	2		1034	4.169355	-0.09173
e	Displacement of people	550	352	144	4	0		1050	4.233871	-0.02722
f	Injury	720	272	102	4	0		1098	4.427419	0.166331
g	Loss of properties	680	304	96	8	0		1088	4.387097	0.126008
H	Psychological stress	540	368	120	12	2		1042	4.201613	-0.05948
	TOTAL								34.08871	Mean= 4.261089

Source: Authors' Field Work, 2023

Discussion of Findings

This study shows that majority of respondents (69%) have firsthand experience of violence and thuggery while only 31% said otherwise and backs up the already established fact that violence before, during or after elections is something of a norm in the Nigerian political sphere.

Violence during the campaign period between opposing political parties and thugs is quite more rampant than violence during and after elections combined.

Most (86.30%) respondents have never participated in any form of electoral violence or thuggery while only 13.70% agreed to have participated one way or the other.

A whopping 96% agreed that the male gender participates most in electoral violence and thuggery as compared to 4% who agreed that it is the female gender.

Corruption, unemployment, inadequate security and lack of integrity from the electoral umpire (INEC) ranked as the causes of violence and thuggery highest with 0.304252, 0.271994, 0.094575 and 0.01393 respectively. What this means is that respondents agreed more that these factors are the main causes of electoral violence and thuggery (significant causes of violence and thuggery on Nigerian general elections) meanwhile respondents rated Misinterpretation of politics, Cultism, Tribalism/ Ethnicity, Lack of democratic culture and Inadequate voters education do not really influence tourism (not significant) with -0.01026, -0.026393, -0.05865, -0.05865 and -0.08284 ratings respectively.

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Conclusion

Political violence manifest in acrimony, assault, assassination, intimidation, harassment, maiming and killing consequently these affect the existing social relationship in the society. This paper has significantly attempted to discuss the causes and effects of political violence in Nigeria. The political violence is an ill wind of social phenomenon, which blows no one any good. In its aftermaths both its perpetrators and victims are losers. Also, that violence is not native to man but rather a consequence of his fallen nature, his actions against the grains of his nature. The steps taken here are aimed at reducing or eradicating political violence such that social relationship will grow. There is no substitute to political violence without bitterness.

Recommendations

Having appraised thuggery and violence in relation to Nigerian general elections, especially in Lagos State, the following recommendations made as follow:

- i. **Improvement/enhancement of security:** There is an urgent need to decentralise the control of the police in order to enhance responsibility, and effectiveness. In the same vein, the government should as a matter of urgency declare a ‘state of emergency’ on Nigerian border porosity, and ensure that the armed security agencies are absolutely accountable for their firearms at all times. This will help in curbing the menace of arms proliferation which has its consequences on elections and political violence in Nigeria.
- ii. **Improved unity:** Causes of electoral violence are traceable to political exclusion and economic deprivation in a situation where there is no level playing ground or field among political parties. Therefore, the recommendations reached by the constitutional conference which gives provision for far-reaching and equitable development among ethnic boundaries should be implemented. This will foster better unity among people and devalue the idea of ethnic superiority as often manifested in the Nigerian polity, in appointments and distribution of resources
- iii. The issue of hate speech and other comments that are liable to inspire violence in our politics must be discouraged with penalties equitable with the measures of the effect of such speeches and actions. It is violence- inspiring for a leader or anyone seeking political position to use such words as “If not me, no other person”, if I fail, no one will go there or succeed”. The government and indeed policy makers/law enforcement agents should look out for such persons for immediate prosecution.
- iv. **Reduction of poverty/Improved employment:** Provisions of employment opportunities are highly recommended. Most people who are usually involved in electoral violence of all nature are unemployed/underemployed youths who the corrupt politicians see as the best for their bid. Unemployment renders a person hopeless and makes him a veritable and available tool for political machinations.

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